

GEOTECHNICAL EVALUATION OF SOILS IN NUMAN AND ITS ENVIRONS, NORTH EAST NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT:

A geotechnical evaluation of some soils in Numan, Adamawa, North –East, Nigeria has been carried out. This was done to determine the suitability of the soils for use as sub-grade/filling, sub-base and base course materials for road construction. The samples were collected from five different areas, at surface and sub-surface levels. The areas are New Demsa, Farei, Dowaya, Numan Town and Imbru. The soil samples were subjected to laboratory investigations in conformity with the American Association of State Highway and Transportation (AASHTO) and the British Standard Institution (BSI) Standard specifications. Results of the geotechnical tests indicate that the proportion passing the BS sieve NO.200 ranges from 20.92% to 39.02% whereas plasticity index and consistency index ranges from 14.05 to 22.01 and 1.42% to 2.16% respectively. The compaction test result revealed an optimum Moisture Content (O.M.C) Value of 11.60% and a maximum Dry Density (M.D.D) Value ranging from 1.91g/cm³ to 2.08g/cm³. The California Bearing Ratio Values ranges from 8% to 24%, whereas the plastic limit values ranges from 30% to 51%. Soils at New Demsa, Farei, Numan Town and Imbru are thus considered suitable for use as sub-grade/filling materials, while the soil at Dowaya is unsuitable for use as sub-grade/filling and sub-base material. This is probably why the road at this area failed after construction.

KEYWORDS: - Geotechnical evaluation, sub-grade/filling, sub-base, base course, laboratory.

BACK GROUND INTRODUCTION

In highway design and construction, careful attention is not only given to sampling and testing of the aggregates which are required to provide a pavement that will be sound and durable; but also to the subsoil materials which will provide support for the pavement (Okagbue and Uma, 1988).

In selecting the route for the highway, one of the important factors considered is the geotechnics of the subsoil. At least a casual study of the subsoil through which the highway must pass is exceedingly helpful. From it the general stability of the area can be determined.

Furthermore experience has shown that sub-soil conditions along a highway route can be a crucial factor in the serviceability and good performance of the highway (Weinert, 1968; Earquhar, 1980). It is therefore very crucial to determine the geotechnical properties of soils in order to establish whether a particular soil is suitable for use as fill, grade or sub-base materials. Some of the roads in Numan area have failed and hence constitute potential hazard to pedestrian and motorists alike because of lack of informed geotechnical data on the sub soil conditions.

Most of the previous work done in the study area are mainly regional (Falconer, 1911) and have described the geology of the Upper Benue Trough in terms of sedimentary and stratigraphic aspects. Subsequently, (Carter et al, 1963) gave some details on the geology, geological structure, hydrology and water quality of the old Northern Nigeria in which the study area is included. Offodile (1976) wrote on the origin of the Benue Trough and Geology of the cretaceous of the valley. Braide (1992) studied the sedimentation and tectonics of the Yola arm of the Benue Trough with emphasis on facies architecture and their provenance significance. Offodile (1976), also gave some details on the sedimentation, tectonics and hydrogeological characteristics of part of the Benue Trough. Head (1988) indicated the various methods to be employed in the treatment of expansive soils and gave out the procedure to be adopted in the laboratory. Obiefuna *et al.*, (1999), gave detailed account of the geological and geotechnical evaluation of selected gully sites in Yola area of Adamawa, north-east, Nigeria and recommended on how to tackle the environmental hazards.

The objective of this study is to determine the geotechnical factors responsible for the suitability of some soils in Numan and its environs. To achieve the objective of this research, the result of the various tests have been analysed and used to proffer ways geared towards constructing durable roads.

STUDY AREA

The study area falls within the savannah belt of the Northern Part of Nigeria. It is located between latitude 9°25'N and 9°30'N and longitude 12° 00'E and 12°09' with an areal of about 172. 05 *km*². The area is bounded to the east by the Nguore Town to the North by the Benue River and to the South by the Chabbai hills. The Southern part which is underlain by the Bima Formation is characterized by high relief. The Northern part constitutes the flood plain of the Benue River, and is characterized by river course alluvium consisting of dark muds which show prominent desiccation cracks during the dry season. The topography thus slopes uniformly from hilly south towards the flood plains in the north (see Fig 1)

Soil types of the area are composed predominantly of sandy loam and sandy clay, which vary from the high lands to low lands. The sandy loams are continuously encountered on the southern portion underlain by the Bima Formation. The sandy clays are the main soil type in the northern part consisting of the flood plain of the Benue River.

The study area lies within the tropical semiarid climatic region and hence consists of wet and dry seasons. The wet (rainfall) season starts in April and end on October. The mean annual rainfall in the area is 1003.5mm. The dry season commences on November and ends in March. The average maximum recorded temperature is 39. 9°C, while the hottest months are March and April.

The trees, rocks and soil in the area have been affected by physical and chemical weathering (denudation). The entire area is mostly covered with weathered materials of residual soils which is underlain by Bima Formation. This means that the strength of the sandstone has been greatly reduced by weathering (Fig.2).

Fig 2: Geological Map of The Study Area.

GEOLOGY OF THE AREA

For the purpose of stratigraphic correlation, the Benue Trough was divided by Cratchley and Jones (1965) into an Upper Benue Trough, Middle Benue Trough, and Lower Benue Trough. The area falls within the Yola Arm of the Upper Benue Trough which is believed to have been formed by wrenching faults tectonics and filled with cretaceous sediments.

Stratigraphical Sequence of the Yola Arm.

According to Carter *et al.*, (1963), the stratigraphic sequence of the Upper Benue Trough begins with Albian to Cenomanian epochs.

It has a varied thickness from 0.5km to about 4.6km (Offoegbu, 1988). Overlying this is a transitional deposit named the Yolde Formation showing both marine and continental characteristics. Cenomanian Yolde Formation which shows intercalation of sandstone, limestone and shale is overlain by Dukul, Jessu, Sekule and Numanha Formations which are thought to be lateral equivalents of the Pindiga Formation in the Gombe Sub-basin.

The Dukul Formation is a limestone shale sequence which marks the beginning of a wide-spread shallow marine transgression during Turonian and coincides with the lower end of the Pindiga Formation in Gombe Sub-basin. The Jessu Formation is the continental equivalent (regression) of the Pindiga Formation. it consist of sandstones, sandy mudstones, shales and lime-stones. Numanha Formation is dominantly marine and is composed of shales mudstones, sandstone and limestone. The lower part consists of grey to black shales with nodular mudstones and contemporaneous lava flows.

The Maastrichtian witnessed the deposition of the carbonaceous Lamja Sandstones in the Yola Arm, a lateral equivalent of the Gombe sandstone intercalated with siltstone and shale with poor quality coal in the Upper Part. Thus, capping the Yola Arm, are the Paleocene basaltic flows with the Kerri-kerri Formation terminating the stratigraphy of the Gombe Sub-basin.

The Bima Formation.

The Bima Formation which is at the base of the stratigraphic sequence in the Yola Arm and currently the most highly studied underlies the study area. It consists essentially of two sedimentary units. These are the Albian Bima Formation found largely in the Southern part and the Quaternary River course alluvium, which dominates in the Northern part of the area. The Bima Sandstone has been weathered in places to loose sands deposits. The river course alluvial deposits are characteristised by sands, clays silty-clay and pebbly sands.

According to Braide (1992), the Bima Formation in the Yola Arm, form a coarsening upward (fining upward) sequences. The coarsening upward sequence is more common in the conglomerates on the margin of the basin and range in thickness between 20-30m. The coarsening upward sequence and fining upward sequence is interpreted as an alluvial fan system which reflect fan –lobe, caused by vertical movements of the basin floor, while the fining –upward sequence are thought to be due to the auto cyclic shifting.

The Bima Sandstone comprises of solely clastic sediments laid down under non-marine conditions and according to Offoegbu (1988), varies in thickness from about 0.5km to 4.6km. It can be divided into three members. Bima 1, Bima 2, and Bima 3, but Bima 1 member out-crops only in the core of the Lamurde Anticline South of Kaltungo in-lier (Braide, 1992). According to Offodile (1976) however, the thickness varies from 100m-3000m with its maximum development at the Lamurde Anticline, where the thickness exceeds 3000m. The Bima 1 member is said to be comprised of about 400m of sandstone and argillaceous rocks. The Bima 2 is made of 800m of coarse sandstones interbedded with clays and shales, while the Bima 3 which is at the top has a thickness of about 1700m and comprised essentially of coarse sandstone.

Field observation in the area shows that the Bima Sandstones outcrops in many locations in the southern portion. The rock outcrops do not show clear sections which hindered determination of thickness of deposits. The rock appear light brown to pink in colour

Both primary and secondary sedimentary structures abound in the area. The rocks indicate cross stratification or beds which are mainly tabular structures consisting of planer beds having regular contacts with basal surfaces.

Results of petro-graphic analysis indicate that sandstone is composed essentially of orthoclase feldspar, quartz with iron oxides occurring as cementing materials. The iron cement gave the rocks their characteristics pinkish colour. The percentage of orthoclase in the rock is greater than that of quartz, thus indicating lack of maturity of the sediments.

Yolde Formation

The Yolde Formation is a variable sequence of sandstone and shale which mark the transition from continental to marine environments. The base of the Formation is defined by first the appearance of marine shale and at the top, the disappearance of sandstone and the commencement of limestone shale deposition. The type of section occurs in Dadiya anticline and is exposed in the stream at Yolde, where 166m thick sedimentary deposits were exposed. In this section, the Bima Sandstone is overlain by bedded sandstone which is followed by alternating sandy mudstone and Shelly limestone. To the east around Jessu, the Formation is represented by about 80m thick sandstones and mudstones with occasional shales and oyster beds. To the west of Yolde and Cham, soft cream massive sandstone with thin shale beds are present, where as Mona marked the occurrence of about 210m thick well bedded sandstone which is overlain by sandy mudstone with thin Shelly limestone.

The Yolde Formation in the study area is believed to be in continuity with those of Bambam and Gombe area. The limestone member of the Yolde Formation is highly fractured and fossiliferous. The Formation consists of a succession of alternating flaggy fine to coarse-grained sands and sandstone, which are intercalated with clays, silts and shales. The beds dip gently to the west beneath younger rocks.

In Numan area, the Yolde Formation consist of cyclically bedded shale limestone-siltstone and sandstone units with each cycle beginning with shale of the base passing upword through siltstone to sandstone. The shales and sandstone unit are best developed in the sampled Numan boreholes which attained a total thickness of about (210m). The lower 25m consist of course to medium grained poorly sorted Bima Sandstone which is overlain by cyclically bedded shale, lime-stone, siltstone and sandstone facies of the Yolde Formation.

HYDROGEOLOGY.

The area consists of two Formations namely; the Yolde and Bima Formation. The Yolde Formation overlies the Bima sandstone and consists of 150m of thinly bedded sandstones, followed by alternating mudstones and Shelly lime-stones. The Yolde Formation is a more promising water bearing formation than the Bima sandstone. Aquifers of the Yolde Formation have given better and reliable yields than those of the Bima Sandstone. Yields of up to 4 lit/sec have been obtained at Gombe and Numan. The water normally occurs under water table condition. However in some places clay beds provide confined artesian or sub-artesian conditions.

In the Lau Sedimentary basins, a number of successful boreholes have been drilled into the Yolde Formation, (Offodile, 1992).

The Bima Sandstone host aquifers that occurs mainly under water table to semi-confining conditions. Most lithologic logs reveal clays and shales or sandy shale horizon, in a predominantly sandstone lithology. These clays or sandy clay horizon occur as lenses.

The saturated thickness of the aquifers ranges from 3m to 206m with mean value of 140.9m. The depth to static water level in the aquifer range from 0.61m to 16.93m in the hand dug wells during the rainy season and between 1.06m and 24.50 during the dry season (Ishaku and Ezeigbo, 2000)

The hydraulic conductivity (k) values of the aquifers ranges from 1.63×10^{-4} cm/s to 9.6×10^{-2} cm/s whereas transmissivity (T) Values range from $8.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^2$ to $3.23 \times 10^{-3} \text{m}^2$ in boreholes in the area (Ishaku and Ezeigbo, 2000).

METHODOLOGY

This research work started with a field reconnaissance survey at point where road failures were noticed. This was achieved with the aid of a topographic map of the area. Pictures of the failure portion or point were taken.

Soil samples were collected at grade, sub base and base levels, with the use of geologic equipments such as geologic hammer, measuring tape, chisel and sample bags for carrying the samples. Five samples were collected at five different pits at sub-surface levels.

Before taking the samples, the faces of the soil were scrapped to remove long exposed Oxidized materials to enable the collection of fairly fresh samples.

Soil samples were collected at base, sub base and grade levels, which were taken to the laboratory for geotechnical analysis. These include the Atterberg limit test, California Bearing Ratio test, compaction test and particle size distribution test. All samples were air dried and lumps broken using a rubbered pistle. This was done to stimulate as much as possible the field condition especially as it affects the use of soil in road construction. Table 1 indicates (a) Sieve analysis test result for Numan and its environs (b) Atterberg limit test result, (c) California bearing ratio test result and (d) Compaction test, for the various places in Numan area where the samples were collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For Numan Town, the result indicated the proportion passing BS Sieve No.200 of the sieve analysis to be 36.4%. The BS sieve, indicate a plastic limit value of 29.0% and liquid limit value of 51%, giving a plasticity index value of 21.10 and consistency index of 2.16. A California bearing ratio value of 8% was revealed where as at the optimum moisture content of 11.6%, a maximum dry density of 1.91g/cm^3 was recorded as shown in Table 1. These results are indicative of sub-grade/filling material. Figures (3a &3b).indicate the plotted graphs of CBR and compaction tests for Numan Town.

At Imbru site, the grain size analysis indicates that the proportion passing the BS sieve No 200 was 39.0%. The AtterBerg limit results indicate the plastic limit value of 15.5% with a liquid limit value of 30%, giving a plasticity index of 14.5 and consistency index value of 1.6 respectively. The CBR test indicate a value of 14%, where as at the optimum moisture content of 9.9%, the maximum dry density value of 1.96g/cm^3 was recorded (Table 1). These results are indicative of sub-grade/filling material.

For New Demsa, the results indicate the proportion passing BS Sieve NO 200 of the sieve analysis to be 29.44%. The same area indicate plastic limit value of 23.7% and liquid limit value of 43%, giving a plasticity index of 19.3 and consistency index of 1.87 respectively

A California Bearing Ratio value of 16% was revealed, whereas at the optimum moisture content of 8.6%, the maximum dry density of 1.97g/cm^3 was recorded (Table 1). Therefore based on the recommendation of American Association of State Highways and Transportation (AASHTO), the soil in New Demsa site is suitable for use as sub-grade/filling material.

For Farei site, the grain size analysis results indicate that the proportion passing the BS sieve No 200 was 20.92%. The Atterberg limit result indicate a plastic limit value of 23.3% with a liquid limit value of 44%, giving a plasticity index of 20.4 and consistency index of 1.91 respectively. Thus, at the optimum moisture content of 7%, the maximum dry density value of 20.08g/cm³ was recorded. The average California Bearing Ratio (CBR) was 24% (Table 1). These results are indicative of a soil that is suitable for use as sub-grade/filling materials according to the American Association of State High ways and Transportation Official (AASHTO).

The result of sieve analysis at Dowaya site, indicate the proportion of samples passing Bs No 200 to be about 38.04%. The Atterberg limit result indicate the a plastic limit value of 24.9% with a liquid limit value of 47%, giving a plasticity index of 2.2 and consistency index value of 1.46. Furthermore at the optimum moisture content of 11%, a maximum dry density value of 1.96g/cm³ was recorded. The average California Bearing Ratio value was 16% (Table 1). These results are thus not indicative of sub-grade/filling material and sub-base material according to AAHTO and BS recommended limit.

The tests result indicate that the soil at Numan town, New Demsa, Farei and Imbru are suitable for use as sub-grade/filling while the soil at Dowaya site is not suitable for use as sub-grade filling and sub-base material. However some parts of the roads at the three sites (Numan town, New Demsa, Farei and Imbru failed probably because of poor work done during construction. The road at Dowaya site failed probably because the values of result exceed the Bristish standard Institution (BS) and (AASHTO) recommended limits (Pictures 1,2,3,4 and plotted graphs (Figures 3a,b, 4, 5a,b, 6a, b)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION.

Geotechnical analyses of some soils in Numan area were carried out. The soils were sampled at grade, sub-based and base levels at New Demsa, Farei, Dowaya, Numan Town and Imbru respectively. The study area is underlain by river course alluvial deposits, the Yolde Formation, and the Bima Formation.

Geotechnical test such as Atterberg limits tests, grain-size distribution, compaction test and California Bearing Ratio test were carried out and used to analyse the soil in the study area. This was done to determine their suitability for use as sub-grade/filling material and sub-base material for road construction.

The results of the analysis indicate that soil of New Demsa, Numan Town and Imbru are suitable for use as Sub-grade/filling materials, while that of Dowaya is not suitable for use as sub-grade/filling and sub-base material. This is probably the cause of the failed road at Dowaya.

The importance of soil laboratory test/quality control test cannot be relegated to the background. This is because they serve as a means for the Engineers, Geologist and scientists to determine the suitability of various soils for construction purpose.

Experts such as Geologists and Engineers should be involved or employed as consultants for the determination of soil nature and properties during construction. This is because soils should under-go various tests according to laid down procedures. Finally professional Engineers should always supervise the construction of roads in order to make sure that proper and specified materials are used.

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S/N	Location	Sieve Analysis Result (proportion passing BS sieve No 200) (%)	ATTERBERG LIMIT				COMPACTION		
			Plastic limit (%)	Liquid limit (%)	Plasticity index	Consistency index (%)	California bearing ratio (%)	OMC (%)	MDD g/cm ³
1	Numan	36.7	29.9	51	21.1	2.16	8	11.6	1.91
2	IMBRU	39.02	15.5	30	14.5	1.66	14	9.9	1.96
3	NEW DEMSA	29.44	23.7	43	19.3	1.87	16	8.6	1.97
4	FARAI	20.92	23.3	44	20.4	1.91	24	7.0	2.08
5	DOWAYA	38.04	24.9	4.0	22.1	1.46	16	11.0	1.96

TABLE1: SUMMARY OF RESULTS OF SOIL TEST MIN THE STUDY AREA

Picture 1: failed portion of the Road at site (2) Farai

Picture: failed portion of the Road at site (3) Dowaya

Picture 3: Failed Portion of the Road at Site (4) Numan Town

Picture 4: Failed Portion of the Road at Site (5) Imbru

Fig. 3a: A PLOT OF CBR FOR NUMAN TOWN

FIG. 3B: A PLOT OF COMPACTION FOR NUMAN TOWN

FIG 4: A PLOT OF COMPACTION FOR NEW DEMSA

FIG 5A: A PLOT OF CBR FOR FARAI

Fig 5B: A PLOT OF COMPACTION FOR FARAI

FIG 6A: A PLOT OF CBR FOR DOWAYA

FIG 6B: A PLOT OF COMPACTION FOR DOWAYA

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